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Glossary of terms

- Capitation - Flat payment for treating a patient
- Fee-for-service - Payment that depends on number of performed physician services
- Pay for performance - Payment that depends on performance measures
- Probability weighting - Tendency of individuals to use weighted probabilities instead of actual probabilities
- Rank-dependent utility function - A utility function that incorporates rank-dependent probability weighting

Abstract

This report consists of a theoretical model and experimental hypotheses concerning effort and referral decisions of a primary care physician tasked with treating chronically ill patients. In terms of financial incentives we consider capitation, fee-for-service, and pay for performance. Further, we consider whether hospital capacity is available or not. In terms of behavioral aspects, we account for different levels of physician altruism, risk aversion, and probability weighting. Hypotheses for a laboratory experiment are derived from the results of the theoretical model.

1 Introduction

In this report, we develop a theoretical model to examine how primary care physicians (PCPs) respond to financial incentives in the management of chronic diseases. Managing these conditions requires effort on the part of physicians. This effort, typically not observable by payers, creates an agency problem between the payer and the PCP, which our analysis focuses on. Furthermore, we consider the possibility that patients are referred to hospital care.

A key innovation in our model is the incorporation of the dynamic nature of chronic care. For this purpose, we consider a two-period model. In period one, the PCP provides preventive effort that enhances the probability that the patient stays in a low severity illness state in period two. In period two, the PCP decides whether or not to refer the patient to hospital care. We vary both the payment system (capitation, fee-for-service, pay for performance) as well as the availability of hospital treatment. For instance, hospital beds may be unavailable during periods extreme events such as a pandemic.

Physicians are assumed to be concerned not only with their own profits but also patient benefit as in Ellis and McGuire (1986). We also consider the impact of risk aversion and probability weighting (Kahneman and Tversky, 1979; Quiggin, 1982; Tversky and Kahneman, 1992) in a rank-dependent utility (RDU) framework to investigate how the uncertain nature of patient benefit affects effort exertion.

Insights from the theoretical model are used to generate hypotheses for testing in a laboratory experiment (Task 6.3, Deliverable 6.4). This experiment will allow us to test whether physician behavior has been modeled appropriately. Additionally, the theoretical model provides a conceptual framework for Task 6.2 (Deliverable 6.2 and 6.3), which aims to analyze incentive effects of existing payment schemes in European countries.

2 Model

A primary care physician provides care for chronically ill patients for two periods. We consider a single representative patient. Let $s_t \in \{l, h\}$ be the severity of the patient's illness in period $t \in \{1, 2\}$. s_t is observable by the PCP at all times. Initially, the patient is only mildly ill ($s_1 = l$). Between periods, the severity of illness can deteriorate. The probability with which this happens depends on the prevention effort $e \in [0, \bar{e}]$ exerted by the PCP in period one. The base probability for staying in the low severity state is \tilde{p} . For each unit of effort, the probability of staying healthy increases by Δ_p : $1 \geq p(e) := Pr(l \rightarrow l|e) = \tilde{p} + e\Delta_p \geq 0$. For our analysis, we normalize effort in such a manner that the patient will be severely ill in period two with certainty if no effort is exerted and he will be mildly ill with certainty if maximum effort is provided, i.e. $\tilde{p} = 0, \bar{e} = 1/\Delta_p$. Exerting effort is costly for the physician with cost function $0 \leq d(e) < \infty$ with $d_e \geq 0, d_{ee} > 0$.

period 1 period 2

Figure 1: Patient states and transition probabilities

The patient has a base level of health \bar{H} . If the patient is severely ill at the start of period two, he suffers a loss of $L \leq \bar{H}$. A part of this loss is recovered by providing treatment for the patient in period two. The PCP decides whether this treatment is provided by herself at costs c_P^h or a hospital H at costs $c_H^h \geq c_P^h$. For PCP treatment, the recovered loss is T_P and for hospital treatment it is $T_H \leq L$ with $T_P \leq T_H$. Further, l -types require treatment in period two to retain their health. It can be provided by the PCP at costs c_P^l or the hospital H at costs $c_H^l \geq c_P^l$ with no difference in treatment benefit between PCP or hospital. However, we will also consider the case that the hospital is at capacity and can not treat new patients of either type. The development of the patient's state is depicted in Figure 1.

The PCP receives a payment Γ for treating the patient. We consider three payment system components: a capitation fee (F), a treatment fee (γ), and a pay-for-performance (ρ) component for keeping patients in mild condition. For example, performance pay could be implemented by using patient surveys. The PCP is assumed to make non-negative profits in expectation: $\mathbb{E}\pi(e) := \mathbb{E}\Gamma(e) - \mathbb{E}C(e) \geq 0$. Furthermore, she is assumed to be altruistic towards the patient with altruism parameter $1 \geq \beta \geq 0$.

2.1 Efficiency

In the following, we analyze efficient referral behavior and effort provision. Considering net benefit as a measure for efficiency, we assume that hospital treatment in period two is efficient for h -types, i.e.,

$$T_H - c_H^h \geq T_P - c_P^h.$$

For l -types, PCP treatment is efficient as hospital treatment generates higher costs for no additional benefits. Next, consider the efficient level of prevention effort. For a risk-neutral payer,

social loss is given by

$$SL(e) = d(e) + (1 - p(e))(L - T_H + c_H^h) + p(e)c_P^l.$$

Therefore, the efficient level of effort e^{FB} is characterized by marginal benefits of effort provision equaling marginal costs.

$$\Delta_p(L - T_H + c_H^h - c_P^l) = d_e(e^{FB}) \quad (1)$$

We assume that this solution exists, i.e. $0 \leq e^{FB} \leq \bar{e}$. Proposition 1 summarizes.

Proposition 1. *First-best efficient effort is characterized by marginal benefits equaling marginal costs. Efficiency in period two is characterized by referring severely ill patients to the hospital and treating mildly ill patients.*

2.2 Provider behavior (linear utility)

Let us consider provider behavior. Initially, we consider risk-neutral expected utility maximizing PCPs. Later, we consider the effects of risk aversion and probability weighting. If the PCP is indifferent between several options, we assume that she chooses the more efficient option.

2.2.1 Capitation

We start by studying incentives under capitation. Under capitation the PCP refers the patient to hospital care in period two if and only if

$$\begin{aligned} \beta(T_H - T_P) + c_P^h &\geq 0 \\ c_P^l &\geq 0 \end{aligned}$$

for h -types and l -types respectively. Therefore, all patients are referred to hospital care, which is inefficient for l -types. Expected utility in period one is given by

$$\mathbb{E}U(e) = F - d(e) - (1 - p(e))\beta[L - T_H].$$

Then she provides effort according to

$$\Delta_p\beta[L - T_H] = d_e(e^{CAP}).$$

The capitation F does not affect incentives. Therefore, it can be set to satisfy the minimum profit constraint. Compared to the efficient Condition (1), even a PCP who values the patient's benefit to the same degree as her own payoff ($\beta = 1$) provides less effort because the cost of hospital care is not internalized by her. Note however that, conditional on all patients being referred, this type of PCP provides efficient effort because effort provision does not save on hospital costs in this case and, consequently, efficient effort is reduced. It follows Proposition 2.

Proposition 2. *Under Capitation all patients are referred to hospital care. Furthermore, effort provision is lower than in the first-best, even for highly altruistic PCPs. Conditional on all patients being referred, PCPs who internalize patient benefit to the same degree as their own profits provide efficient effort.*

2.2.2 Treatment fee

In order to prevent the referral of l -types, the payer can employ a treatment fee γ in addition to the capitation. The PCP refers a patient for hospital treatment in period two if and only if

$$\begin{aligned}\beta(T_H - T_P) - \gamma + c_P^h &\geq 0 \\ c_P^l - \gamma &\geq 0\end{aligned}$$

for h -types and l -types respectively. Expected utility in period one is given by

$$\mathbb{E}U(e) = \begin{cases} F - d(e) - (1 - p(e))(\beta[L - T_P] - \gamma + c_P^h) + p(e)(\gamma - c_P^l), & \gamma > \beta(T_H - T_P) + c_P^h \\ F - d(e) - (1 - p(e))\beta[L - T_H] + p(e)(\gamma - c_P^l), & c_P^l \leq \gamma \leq \beta(T_H - T_P) + c_P^h \\ F - d(e) - (1 - p(e))\beta[L - T_H], & c_P^l > \gamma \end{cases}$$

for the cases in which she refers all patients, refers only h -types, and refers no patients respectively. Therefore, she provides effort in period one according to

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta_p(\beta[L - T_P] + c_P^h - c_P^l) &= d_e(\tilde{e}_T), \\ \Delta_p(\beta[L - T_H] + \gamma - c_P^l) &= d_e(\tilde{e}) \text{ or} \\ \Delta_p\beta[L - T_H] &= d_e(\tilde{e}_R).\end{aligned}$$

Figure 2 depicts the impact of γ on e and treatment decisions assuming $d(e) = ae^2$. Figure 2a shows a PCP with little altruism and Figure 2b shows a highly altruistic PCP. Without a treatment fee, the more altruistic physician already exerts more effort. Increasing γ to c_P^l makes the PCP indifferent between treating and referring l -type patients independently of physician altruism. This shifts behavior in the second period without affecting effort provision. Increasing γ beyond c_P^l , enhances effort provision because the treatment of l -types gets more profitable relative to h -types. This is so because l -types are treated by the PCP and h -types are referred to the hospital as long as γ is not too large. γ can be increased until $\tilde{\gamma} := \beta(T_H - T_P) + c_P^h$ without incentivizing the treatment of h -types. However, in order to implement efficient effort it is necessary and sufficient to increase γ to $\gamma^{eFB} := (1 - \beta)(L - T_H) + c_P^h$. This implies that efficient effort and referrals can be implemented simultaneously by paying γ^{eFB} if and only if $\beta \geq \bar{\beta} := \frac{c_P^h - c_P^l + L - T_H}{L - T_P}$. Conversely, if $\beta < \bar{\beta}$, γ cannot be increased sufficiently to implement efficient effort. Lemma 1 summarizes results under FFS so far.

Lemma 1. *If $\gamma = c_P^l$, all h -types and no l -types are referred to hospital care. Effort is identical to $\gamma = 0$ case.*

If $\gamma = c_P^h$, effort is larger compared to $\gamma = c_P^l$ and referral behavior is identical.

If $\gamma = \gamma^{eFB}(\bar{\beta})$, effort is larger compared to $\gamma = c_P^h$ and referral of h -types decreases. Furthermore, $\tilde{e} \geq e^{FB}$ for $\beta \geq \bar{\beta}$. Increasing γ further, only incentivizes inefficiently large effort.

Figure 3 depicts the second-best optimal treatment fee γ^{SB} if altruism is known. In this case, increasing γ beyond $\tilde{\gamma}$ is not efficient as it incentivizes the treatment of h -types by the PCP without enhancing effort. Consequently, under FFS, PCPs should be incentivized to only refer h -types. PCPs with $\beta \geq \bar{\beta}$ should receive γ^{eFB} to implement efficient effort exertion. For these PCPs, optimal payment decreases in β . Less altruistic PCPs should receive $\tilde{\gamma}$ to maximize effort without adversely affecting referral incentives. For these PCPs, optimal payment increases in β . Taken together we get $\gamma^{SB} = \min(\tilde{\gamma}, \gamma^{eFB})$.

Figure 2: Impact of treatment fee γ on exerted effort \tilde{e} and treatment decisions given $d(e) = ae^2$

Figure 3: Second-best optimal treatment fee γ^{SB} if altruism is known

If altruism is unknown, the second-best optimal treatment fee lies between c_P^h and $\gamma^{eFB}(\bar{\beta})$. A higher fee within this interval potentially increases effort while potentially leading to under-referral of h -types by weakly altruistic PCPs. Increasing effort beyond $\gamma^{eFB}(\bar{\beta})$, leads to a supply of inefficiently large effort because only PCPs with $\beta > \bar{\beta}$ are affected. However, these physicians already provide at least efficient effort.

Proposition 3. *Efficient referrals can be implemented by paying a treatment fee that lies between the PCP's treatment costs for mildly and severely ill patients. Efficient levels of effort can be implemented if PCPs are sufficiently altruistic and altruism is known. Otherwise, effort is distorted.*

For unknown altruism, effort can be improved without adversely affecting referrals by paying the treatment costs for severely ill patients. Increasing treatment fees further, increases effort at the cost of generating under-referrals for PCPs with low level of altruism.

2.2.3 Performance pay

Assume that the payer can verify whether the patient is mildly ill in period two. In this case he pays a performance fee ρ in addition to the capitation and treatment fee if the patient is not ill in period two.¹ This fee does not affect the treatment decision in period two. From now on we assume that the treatment fee is such that the PCP treats only l -types, i.e. $\gamma \in [c_P^l, \tilde{\gamma}]$. Expected utility in period one is given by

$$\mathbb{E}U(e) = F - d(e) - (1 - p(e))\beta[L - T_H] + p(e)(\gamma - c_P^l + \rho).$$

¹An alternative is to pay a fee if the patient did not get referred to hospital care. However, incentives are identical to the treatment fee case.

The PCP provides effort according to

$$\Delta_p(\beta[L - T_H] + \gamma - c_P^l + \rho) = d_e(e^{PFP}).$$

Consequently, the level of ρ that implements efficient effort is

$$\rho^{PFP} = (1 - \beta)[L - T_H] - \gamma + c_H^h.$$

If altruism is known, performance pay improves on FFS by ensuring that PCPs with $\beta < \bar{\beta}$ can be incentivized to provide efficient effort. If altruism is unknown, an increase in ρ increases effort but may lead to inefficiently high effort for altruistic physicians given that $e^{FB} < \bar{e}$. Proposition 4 summarizes.

Proposition 4. *Performance pay increases effort without affecting referral incentives.*

If altruism is known, the payer can always set the P4P fee to implement efficient effort by internalizing both partial patient benefit from an avoided hospitalization and the hospital costs for severely ill patients net the PCP's treatment fee. If altruism is unknown, effort may be inefficiently large for altruistic PCPs.

2.2.4 Hospital capacity

In times of high demand for hospital treatment, hospital capacity may be limited. One example is the Corona crisis. We study the impacts of a lack of hospital capacity on PCP prevention effort. If there is no hospital capacity, all patients are treated by the PCP. If the PCP does not prefer to refer any patients, capacity constraints are immaterial.

If the PCP prefers to refer h -types to hospital care and treat l -types, the lack of hospital capacity increases the expected negative impact from having a patient in severe condition relative to the mild condition. The condition describing effort provision switches from

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_p(\beta[L - T_H] + \gamma - c_P^l + \rho) &= d_e(e^{PFP}) \text{ to} \\ \Delta_p(\beta[L - T_P] + c_P^h - c_P^l + \rho) &= d_e(e^{PFP_T}). \end{aligned}$$

In addition to preventing a higher net loss for the patient, higher effort also prevents high treatment costs for the PCP. However, treatment fees no longer increase the marginal benefit of effort provision. Consequently, marginal benefit of effort provision increases by $\Delta_{H1} := \beta(T_H - T_P) + c_P^h - \gamma$.

For PCPs who prefer to refer both types, the condition describing effort provision switches from

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_p(\beta[L - T_H] + \rho) &= d_e(e^{PFP_R}) \text{ to} \\ \Delta_p(\beta[L - T_P] + c_P^h - c_P^l + \rho) &= d_e(e^{PFP_T}). \end{aligned}$$

Consequently, the marginal return to providing effort increases by $\Delta_{H2} := \beta(T_H - T_P) + c_P^h - c_P^l$.

Next, we show that the effect of constrained hospital capacity on effort is stronger if the PCP prefers to refer both patient types. It holds $\Delta_{H2} - \Delta_{H1} = \gamma - c_P^l$. The PCP prefers to treat l -types if and only if $\gamma \geq c_P^l$. Therefore, the effect of limited hospital capacity is stronger if both patient types are referred without capacity constraints, i.e. capacity constraints have a greater impact if $\gamma < c_P^l$ than if $\gamma \in [c_P^l, c_P^h]$. It follows Proposition 5.

Proposition 5. *For PCPs who prefer to refer at least one patient type, hospital capacity constraints increase exerted effort. This effect is stronger if treatment fees do not cover the costs of the treatment for mildly ill patients.*

2.3 Provider behavior (rank-dependent utility maximization)

When individuals are confronted with uncertain, gain-framed prospects, they tend to exhibit risk aversion and engage in probability weighting (Kahneman and Tversky, 1979; Quiggin, 1982; Tversky and Kahneman, 1992). Small probabilities tend to be over weighted, whereas large probabilities tend to be under weighted. This is relevant for the exertion of prevention effort as we will show below.

Prevention behavior under probability weighting has been studied in RDU (Etner and Jeleva, 2013) and Prospect Theory (Baillon et al., 2022) frameworks. Authors in both papers show that probability weighting can lead to underprevention if individuals are insensitive to changes in probability. Bleichrodt (2022) surveys the literature on prevention and finds that prudence, probability weighting, and loss aversion can affect prevention behavior. Generally, risk aversion tends to have weak, indeterminate effects. Therefore, we focus primarily on the impact of probability weighting in this paper.

We assume that individuals evaluate gains in terms of profit and altruistic component with the function $u(x) = x^\sigma$.² Probabilities are weighted with $w(p) = \frac{1}{e^{\ln(1/p)^\alpha}}$ as proposed by Prelec (1998). $\sigma \in (0, 1]$ measures an individual's risk aversion and $\alpha \in (0, 1]$ measures the degree of probability weighting with risk-neutrality for $\sigma = 1$ and no weighting for $\alpha = 1$. For $p < 1/e$ the weighting function is concave, whereas it is convex for larger values. Under rank-dependent probability weighting, the probability weight is calculated for the larger payoff, in this case the payoff when the patient is mildly ill.

Concerning referral decisions, predictions from the RDU model are identical to predictions from the linear model. Referral decisions are unaffected by probability weighting because they are decisions under certainty. To confirm that the concave utility function does not change behavior, consider any two referral strategies that give rise to payoffs x_1 and x_2 . It holds $u(x_1) \leq u(x_2) \iff x_1 \leq x_2$. Therefore, referral decisions are identical between the models. Furthermore, since the linear model is a special case of the RDU model with $\alpha = \sigma = 1$, any predictions regarding effort from the linear model are also consistent with the RDU model. Therefore, in this section, we focus on predictions regarding the impact of performance pay on effort provision that are specific to the RDU model. This allows us to compare the models in the experiment. We continue to assume that the treatment fee is such that the PCP treats only l -types, i.e. $\gamma \in [c_P^l, \tilde{\gamma}]$.

Expected (perceived, rank-dependent) utility in period one is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}U(e) = & (1 - w[p(e)])(F - d(e) + \beta[\bar{H} - L + T_H])^\sigma + \\ & w[p(e)](F - d(e) + \beta\bar{H} + \gamma - c_P^l + \rho)^\sigma \end{aligned}$$

Let $x_l \geq x_h \geq 0$ be the PCP's payoffs (including the altruism component) for l - and h -types respectively. Then the partial derivative by e is:

$$\mathbb{E}U_e = \Delta_p w_p[p](x_l^\sigma - x_h^\sigma) - \sigma d_e \{ (x_h^{\sigma-1})(1 - w[p]) + (x_l^{\sigma-1})w[p] \} \quad (2)$$

The left part of Condition (2) represents the marginal benefits of exerting effort, whereas the right part represents the marginal costs. For the rest of this section we assume $x_l > x_h > 0$. For this inequality to hold, it is sufficient to assume $\beta > 0$, $\gamma > c_P^l$, or $\rho > 0$. Lemma 2 states important comparative statics.³

²All payoffs are (framed as) positive, therefore we do not consider negative payoffs and loss aversion.

³Note that for any internal maximum e^{int} , it holds $\mathbb{E}U_{ee}(e^{int}) < 0$. Therefore, by applying implicit derivation, the signs of the expressions in Lemma 2 correspond to the signs of e_x^{int} for the respective $x \in \{\beta, \rho\}$.

Lemma 2.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{E}U_{e\beta} &= \sigma\{\Delta_p w_p[p](x_l^{\sigma-1}\bar{H} - x_h^{\sigma-1}(\bar{H} - L + T_H)) + \\ &\quad d_e(1 - \sigma)[x_h^{\sigma-2}(\bar{H} - L + T_H)(1 - w[p]) + x_l^{\sigma-2}\bar{H}w[p]\} > 0 \\ \mathbb{E}U_{e\rho} &= \sigma\{\Delta_p w_p[p](x_l^{\sigma-1}) + d_e(1 - \sigma)[x_h^{\sigma-2}(1 - w[p])]\} > 0\end{aligned}$$

Unsurprisingly, increasing altruism and performance pay increases effort exertion. Note that $\mathbb{E}U_e$ increases if both the slope w_p and size w of the weighting function increase. This insight is key to understanding the impact of probability weighting on prevention effort. Using the terms of Etner and Jeleva (2013), Definition 1 defines relative fatalism.

Definition 1. Consider two PCPs who only differ by their degree of probability weighting α . PCP A is more fatalist than PCP B for a given range of probabilities (p_{\min}, p_{\max}) if and only if $w^A(p) \leq w^B(p)$ and $w_p^A(p) \leq w_p^B(p) \forall p \in (p_{\min}, p_{\max})$.

Etner and Jeleva (2013) show that a less fatalist individual invests more in self-protection if expected rank-dependent utility is concave. The same argument holds true for PCPs in our setting⁴. If PCPs are more sensitive to changes in probability, i.e. their weighting function is more steep, an increase in effort is perceived to be more valuable because the perceived change in probability due to effort exertion is larger. Furthermore, if PCPs have larger probability weights for a given probability, their expected payoff rises and, therefore, the marginal costs of effort provision are felt less for risk averse PCPs.

To visualize the implications of probability weighting on the exertion of prevention effort, consider Figure 4a and 4b. Figure 4a depicts a probability weighting function with $\alpha = 0.5$. Actual probabilities p are depicted on the x-axis and perceived probabilities $w(p)$ are depicted on the y-axis. The three pairs of points in Figure 4a have the same difference within them in terms of actual probability p . However, if actual probabilities are either very small (A^1 and A^2) or very large (C^1 and C^2), differences in perceived probabilities are larger than for medium values of actual probabilities (B^1 and B^2).

Let us consider the three cases in which p is close to zero, medium sized, or close to one. In the first case, both w and w_p are larger for an individual who weighs probabilities compared to one that does not. Therefore, probability weighting PCPs are less fatalist than utility maximizers in this area. If $p \in (1/e, \bar{p})$, with \bar{p} being defined by $w_p[\bar{p}] = 1$, the opposite is true. This can be seen in Figure 4b. Both the probability weight and slope are smaller for the weighting individual, implying greater fatalism. Lemma 3 shows that if the probability space is restricted to medium values on which $\mathbb{E}U$ is concave, a probability weighting individual provides less effort than a non-weighting individual *ceteris paribus*.

Lemma 3. Let the probability space be restricted on $p \in (1/e, p^{\max})$, i.e. $e \in (\frac{1}{\Delta_p e}, p^{\max}/\Delta_p)$, and let

- a) $\mathbb{E}U_{ee} < 0$ on $(\frac{1}{\Delta_p e}, p^{\max}/\Delta_p)$ and
- b) $p^{\max} \leq \bar{p}$.

Then, *ceteris paribus*, a probability weighting PCP provides less effort than a utility maximizing PCP.

⁴In our setting PCPs “self-protect” in the sense that they prevent a loss of profit and altruistic benefit by exerting effort.

(a) $\alpha = 0.5$

(b) $\alpha = [0.3, 0.5, 0.8]$

Figure 4: Example of a probability weighting function. The dashed red line indicates no weighting.

Proof. Let e_1^* and e_2^* be local maxima of the probability weighting PCP and the utility maximizing PCP respectively. Following the proof of Proposition 10 in Etner and Jeleva (2013), it needs to be shown that

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathbb{E}U_e^1|_{e=e_2^*} < |\mathbb{E}U_e^2|_{e=e_2^*} &\iff \\ \Delta_p w_p^1 (x_l^\sigma - x_h^\sigma) - \sigma d_e \{ (x_h^{\sigma-1})(1-w^1) + (x_l^{\sigma-1})w^1 \} & \\ < \Delta_p (x_l^\sigma - x_h^\sigma) - \sigma d_e \{ (x_h^{\sigma-1})(1-p) + (x_l^{\sigma-1})p \} & \end{aligned}$$

This inequality follows from $w^1 < p$ and $w_p^1 < 1$. \square

Finally, consider probabilities close to one. It holds $\lim_{p \nearrow 1} w_p = \infty$. This implies that the (positive) difference in utility between l - and h -types weighs heavily compared to the marginal cost of effort provision in Condition (2). Consequently, a small increase in effort, and therefore in p , yields an increase in rank-dependent expected utility for an altruistic PCP. Since d is bounded, $\lim_{p \nearrow 1} \mathbb{E}U_e(\bar{e}) = \infty$. Therefore, there exists a local maximum for $e' = \bar{e}$. Lemma 4 shows existing local maxima.

Lemma 4. *Let $\alpha < 1$. There exists a local maximum of $\mathbb{E}U$ at $e' = \bar{e}$.*

Let $\gamma = c_P^l$. There exists at least one local maximum of $\mathbb{E}U$ at $e'' \in [0, \bar{e})$ if β and ρ are sufficiently small.

Proof. The first statement has already been proved above. Considering the second statement: Because $\mathbb{E}U_e$ is continuous, proving $\mathbb{E}U_e < 0$ for any value is sufficient to prove the existence of a local maximum on the given left-closed interval. For $\gamma = c_P^l$ and $\beta, \rho \rightarrow 0$ it follows $x_l \rightarrow x_h$. Therefore, $\mathbb{E}U_e < 0$. \square

Figure 5 depicts an example for rank-dependent expected utility of a PCP for different values of σ and α .⁵ Whereas expected utility is concave under no probability weighting, this is no longer the case if the PCP weighs probabilities. Consequently, two local maxima emerge, an inner maximum and a corner solution. Note that the inner maximum is shifted to the left compared to the inner maximum under no probability weighting. The risk aversion parameter σ only has a minor influence on expected utility in this example.

Next, we consider the impact of a change in performance pay ρ on the global maximum point given $\alpha < 1$. Let $e'' \in [0, \bar{e})$ be the global maximum point for a given, sufficiently small ρ and β . Since $\mathbb{E}U_{e\rho} > 0$, there is a critical $\tilde{\rho}$ for which $\mathbb{E}U(e'') = \mathbb{E}U(\bar{e})$. As $\lim_{p \nearrow 1} \mathbb{E}U_e > 0$, e'' does not converge to \bar{e} for $\rho \rightarrow \tilde{\rho}$. Consequently, an increase in ρ beyond $\tilde{\rho}$ causes a discontinuous jump in effort towards \bar{e} . It follows Lemma 5.

Lemma 5. *Let $\alpha < 1$, let $E''(\rho)/\bar{e}$ be the set of global maximum points excluding \bar{e} , and let $e'' = \max_\rho(E''/\bar{e})$ be the largest value from this set.*

It is not possible to implement any efforts $e \in (e'', \bar{e})$ as a global maximum.

From Lemma 5 it follows that if $e^{FB} \in (e'', \bar{e})$, it is impossible to implement e^{FB} with the help of performance pay ρ .

Figure 6 depicts globally optimal effort levels e^* for the PCP depending on α , β , and ρ . In Figure 6a, we vary α and β and set $\rho = 0$. In Figure 6b, we vary α and ρ and set $\beta = 0$. Unsurprisingly, comparing Figure 6a and 6b shows that the impact of an increase in β and ρ are nearly identical. Whereas the influence of β and ρ on e^* is monotonously positive, the

⁵Unless specified otherwise, the simulations in Figure 5 and 6 are based on the following parameters: $F = 130, H = 100, \Delta_p = 0.2, \bar{p} = 1, \beta = 0.7, \sigma = 1, L = 71, T_H = 30, T_P = 5, c_H^h = 10, c_P^l = 1, \gamma = 1, \rho = 0, d(e) = e^2$, which implies $e^{FB} = \bar{e} = 5$.

Figure 5: Example for expected utility under CPT

influence of α is not monotonous. For high levels of altruism or performance pay, stronger probability weighting can increase effort, whereas it can decrease effort for smaller levels of altruism or performance pay. This leads to a polarization of behavior for PCPs who strongly weigh probabilities. For these physicians, there exists critical values of β and ρ for which there is a large jump in effort to $e^* = \bar{e}$. This is due to the change of local maximum from e'' to $e' = \bar{e}$. Proposition 6 summarizes results.

Proposition 6. (i) Under RDU, multiple expected rank-dependent utility maxima emerge for exerted effort. There always exists a local maximum for the maximum level of effort. Increasing performance pay may induce a switch from one local maximum to another, leading to a discontinuous jump in effort.

(ii) If the range of effort is restricted to a medium size, probability weighting PCPs provide less effort than expected utility maximizers ceteris paribus.

Figure 6: Predicted levels of PCP effort e^* (global maximum point) under CPT ($\sigma = 1$)
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3 Experimental Design

For the cost function, we define $d(e) = e^2$. We use the following parameters as our baseline \mathcal{A} : $F = 130, H = 100, \Delta_p = 0.2, \bar{p} = 1, L = 71, T_H = 30, T_P = 5, c_H^l = 5, c_H^h = 10, c_P^l = 1, c_P^h = 5$, which implies $e^{FB} = \bar{e} = 5$ and $\bar{\beta} = 0.7$.

Parameter Set \mathcal{B} is defined as a deviation from the Baseline Set \mathcal{A} . We define it by setting $T_H = 40$, which implies $e^{FB} = 4$ and $\bar{\beta} = 0.55$. With Parameter Set \mathcal{B} we can test the case that a submaximal effort level is efficient. In both parameter sets, the PCPs always earn more than the patients.

Our treatments are shown in Table 1. In Treatment \mathcal{CAP} , only a capitation is paid. In Treatment \mathcal{FFS} , a treatment fee is paid in addition to the capitation. Treatment \mathcal{PFP} adds an additional pay-for-performance component. Extreme events such as the Covid pandemic are considered in Treatment \mathcal{EE} . In this treatment, no hospital capacity is available. Lastly, Treatment \mathcal{LIM} limits the range of effort that can be exerted by the PCP. In this treatment, the state of the patient in period two is always uncertain.

For the parametrization of γ and ρ we choose values that are of theoretical interest. Besides the values in Table 1, we also test in between values.

T	F	γ	ρ	e	H
\mathcal{CAP}	130	0	0	[0, 5]	Y
\mathcal{FFS}	130	$[0, c_P^l, c_P^l + 1, c_P^h, c_P^h + (1 - \bar{\beta})(L - T_H)]$	0	[0, 5]	Y
\mathcal{PFP}	130	$c_P^l + 1$	$[0, c_H^h - \gamma, c_H^h + L - T_H - \gamma]$	[0, 5]	Y
\mathcal{EE}	130	0	0	[0, 5]	N
\mathcal{LIM}	130	0	0	[2, 3]	Y

Table 1: Treatments

4 Hypotheses

In this section we state our hypotheses for the linear and RDU model. Hypotheses are divided into qualitative and quantitative hypotheses. For each PCP we estimate behavioral parameters $\hat{\beta}$, $\hat{\sigma}$, and $\hat{\alpha}$ from independent tasks. RDU parameters $\hat{\sigma}$, and $\hat{\alpha}$ are estimated according to the method laid out in Tanaka et al. (2010). Altruism parameter $\hat{\beta}$ is estimated by a simplified version of our effort provision task with certain payoffs. For this task, PCPs start with 130 tokens and can increase the payoff of the patient by exerting effort e . The patient receives a payoff of 59 if no effort is exerted. For each unit of effort, a patient receives 8.2 tokens, with the maximum payout being 100 for $e = 5$. The effort comes at cost e^2 to the physician. Note that this task is identical to the task described in Section 2 when the hospital treats h -types, payouts are certain, and Parameter Set \mathcal{A} is used. With this task it is possible to estimate $\hat{\beta}_A = 2e/8.2$. The game is then repeated with effort benefit fitted to Parameter Set \mathcal{B} . In this case, the patient receives 6.2 tokens per unit of effort and $\hat{\beta}_B = 2e/6.2$. For the quantitative hypotheses, $\hat{\beta}_A$ and $\hat{\beta}_B$ are used as estimates for β when testing the respective parameter sets. The quantitative hypotheses are valid only for our estimated parameters. We assume that all parameters have support everywhere on $[0, 1]$.

Whereas hypotheses for the linear model are also consistent with the RDU model for $\sigma = \alpha = 1$, none of the RDU model predictions for $\alpha < 1$ hold for the linear model. As such, we can assess the relative predictive accuracy of these models by comparing whether the RDU hypotheses are in line with the data.

4.1 Qualitative hypotheses

4.1.1 Linear model

Hypothesis L1. *Treatment CAP: all patients are referred to hospital care in period two.*

Hypothesis L1 follows from Proposition 2.

Hypothesis L2. *Treatment FFS: if $\gamma = c_P^l$, all h -types and no l -types are referred to hospital care. Effort is identical to $\gamma = 0$ case.*

If $\gamma = c_P^h$, effort is larger compared to $\gamma = c_P^l$ and referral behavior is identical.

If $\gamma = c_P^h + (1 - \bar{\beta})(L - T_H)$, effort is larger compared to $\gamma = c_P^h$ and referral of h -types decreases.

Hypothesis L2 follows from Lemma 1.

Hypothesis L3. *Treatment PFP: Increasing ρ increases effort and does not affect referrals.*

Hypothesis L3 follows from Proposition 4.

Hypothesis L4. *Effort in Treatment $\mathcal{E}\mathcal{E}$ is larger than effort in Treatment FFS for any level of γ .*

Parameter Set \mathcal{B} : Compared to Treatment FFS with $\gamma = c_P^h + (1 - \bar{\beta})(L - T_H)$, only inefficiently large effort is exerted additionally.

Hypothesis L4 follows from Proposition 5 and Lemma 1.

4.1.2 RDU model

Hypothesis PT1. *Treatment PFP: Increasing ρ leads to jumps in effort provision towards $e = \bar{e}$.*

Hypothesis PT1 follows from Proposition 6(i). A jump in Hypothesis PT1 is defined in the following way. Let ρ increase from ρ_1 to ρ_2 . If $e(\rho_2) = \bar{e}$ and $e(\rho_2) - e(\rho_1)$ is sufficiently larger than would be expected from the linear model, then a jump has occurred. For our parameter sets, the linear model predicts

$$e^{PPF}(\rho_2) - e^{PPF}(\rho_1) = \frac{\Delta_p(\rho_2 - \rho_1)}{2} = 0.1.$$

Sufficiently larger means that for $\kappa \geq 1$,

$$\bar{e} - e(\rho_1) > \frac{\kappa}{10}.$$

A larger κ implies a stricter criterion of whether a jump has occurred. We test Hypothesis PT1 for $\kappa = 1$ and $\kappa = 2$.

4.2 Quantitative hypotheses

For our quantitative hypotheses we need to define conditions under which we classify a PCP as probability weighting according to RDU. We define that for these PCP $\hat{\alpha} \leq 0.8$ and $\hat{\sigma} \leq 1$ must hold. Furthermore, (risk-averse) expected utility maximizers are defined by $1.2 \geq \hat{\alpha} > 0.8$ and $\hat{\sigma} \leq 1$.

4.2.1 Linear model

Hypothesis L5. *Treatment FFS: If $\gamma = c_p^h + (1 - \bar{\beta})(L - T_H)$, PCPs with $\hat{\beta} \geq \bar{\beta}$ provide at least e^{FB} .*

Hypothesis L5 follows from Lemma 1.

4.2.2 RDU model

Hypothesis PT2. *Treatment LLM: Effort is smaller for probability weighting PCPs compared to expected utility maximizing PCPs.*

Hypothesis PT2 is valid only if there is no correlation between $\hat{\alpha}$ and $\hat{\beta}$.⁶ The effort range in Treatment LLM was chosen in such a manner as to ensure that both w and w_p are relatively larger for expected utility maximizers. Furthermore, EU is strictly concave on the interval. Therefore, Lemma 3 applies.

Hypothesis PT3. *Treatment PFP: probability weighting PCPs do not play $e \in (3.1, 5)$.*

The lower end of the effort range in Hypothesis PT3 was determined by means of numerical simulation applied to Lemma 5.

5 Conclusion

This report provides a theoretical model analyzing incentives for PCPs who treat chronically ill patients. It aims to understand how different incentive structures impact referral decisions to a hospital as well as prevention efforts. We consider three different payment systems: capitation, treatment fees, and performance pay. Furthermore, we consider the impact of limited hospital

⁶MG: We may need to adjust for $\hat{\beta}$ in the analysis if this assumption is false.

capacity. We examine the impact of physician altruism, risk aversion, and probability weighting within an RDU framework. Finally, experimental hypotheses are developed to test our theoretical findings.

Under a capitation, PCPs refer all patients to hospitals, which is inefficient for patients with less severe illnesses. Furthermore, the capitation fee provides insufficient effort incentives, leading to sub-optimal effort, even for strongly altruistic PCPs.

When a treatment fee is introduced alongside the capitation system, it can prevent the referral of less severely ill patients. A medium-sized fee can also enhance effort provision. Adjusting the treatment fee to an optimal level can lead to efficient referrals and efforts if PCPs have a high degree of altruism.

We also examine a performance pay system, where PCPs are compensated additionally for keeping patients in the less severe state. For utility maximizing physicians, any desired effort level can be implemented as long as physician altruism is known. In contrast, for probability weighting physicians, the reaction to an increase in performance pay can be discontinuous due to the existence of multiple local maxima. Furthermore, we show that if possible efforts are restricted to a medium range, a probability weighting PCP will provide less effort than a utility maximizing PCP *ceteris paribus*.

Lastly, in scenarios with limited hospital capacity, the model suggests an increase in PCP effort, especially when the treatment fees are insufficient to cover the costs of treating less severely ill patients. This change can be attributed to the higher relative cost of having a patient in a severe condition.

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